

HYBRID OF RF+XGB TO IMPROVE THE TREE-BASED ALGORITHMS IN PREDICTING THE USER LEARNING STYLE IN ONLINE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Learning style of specific users in an online learning system is determined based on their interaction and behaviour towards the system. The most common online learning theory used in determining the learning style is the Felder-Silvermans Theory (FSLSM). Previous researchers have proposed many machine learning algorithms to detect the learning style automatically. This is done by using the log files attributes from the online learning system. However, the percentage of accuracy in the learning style prediction is still low which is only between 58%-91%. With that, this research is conducted to improve the learning style prediction in terms of its accuracy. This is done by doing a hybrid between Random Forest (RF) and Extreme Gradient Boosting (Xgb). Hybrid is needed to further improve the performance of the algorithm in learning style prediction in terms of its percentage of accuracy. From the experiments, the hybrid of RF+Xgb has been proven to be the most effective method, with the accuracy improvement from 87% to 96%.

1 INTRODUCTION

Identifying a student's learning style has several benefits, such as making students aware of their

strength and weaknesses when it comes to learning. It is also meant to be used in determining the learning preferences of each student either in a traditional classroom or through an online learning based system [1].

An online learning based system can be defined as an online system where there is interaction between students and system [2]. Initially, in an online learning based system, the learning style of the user is determined by using available learning style questionnaires based on the selected learning style model. The most commonly used learning style model is the FSLSM. It also incorporates different elements from different learning style models such as Kolb, Pask and Myers-Briggs [3]. However, when students are asked to fill in the questionnaire, the students take a longer time to fill it as the questions are long. Furthermore, students tend to refuse spending too much time on the questionnaire. This causes them to put in random answers [4].

So with that, researchers came out with a new alternative where they determine the learning style automatically [3]. This is done by collecting log files of the interactive behaviour of the user with the system. This consists of the number of mouse clicks, the time taken to do the task, number of views towards certain materials, and others. These attributes were then matched with the learning

style model that they had chose. From there, the results obtained are analyzed further and the learning style of the user is revealed.

In this paper the used of tree-based algorithms was highlighted as a classifier in predicting the learning style. The chosen tree-based algorithm is RF and Xgb which highlighted the used of bagging and boosting method. Both of this algorithm were hybrid in order to improve further the performance of the algorithm in increasing the percentage of accuracy in predicting the learning style of the user.

2 PROPOSED WORK

2.1 Data Selection

The data used in this paper was taken from a research done by Renato [5]. The data is collected from the year 2012 to 2016. It contains a record of 507 students enrolled in Computer Technology courses which have successfully completed the Computer Programming 1 subject. This dataset consists of 15 different attributes. Table 1 shows the different attributes involved which is then divided into the respective dimensions of learning style according to the FSLSM theory. These attributes are then matched to a learning style model specified by the researcher. In this case, FSLSM is used which consists of four different dimensions. The dimensions involved are Input, Processing, Perception and Understanding.

2.2 Method

In order to improve the performance of the tree based algorithm model in predicting the learning style, this research proposed to do a hybrid on the tree-based algorithm. In this proposed hybrid of RF+Xgb, RF act as the baseline model. To improve further the RF model the function obtain from Xgb is merged in the model and new function which hybrid the two algorithms is formed. The parameter involve in RF is *ntrree* and *mtry*

while for the Xgb, the parameter involved is name as *nround*, *c*, *eta*, λ , and α value. The pseudocode of the proposed hybrid algorithm is shown in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Hybrid of RF+Xgb

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1: procedure RF+XGB(nrounds,c,eta,lambda,alpha)
2:   for each class,  $C_i \in D$ , do
3:     Specify the trControl with 5 fold of cross-validation and grid
     search
4:   end for
5:   for RF functions do
6:     Draw ntrree bootstrap samples
7:     For each bootstrap sample, grow un-pruned tree by choosing
     best split based of random sample of mtry prediction at each node
8:     t:optimize mtry to reduce OOB error
9:   end for
10:  for t, use (D), do
11:    specify the supporting parameter of model t and ntrree
12:    Determine best mtry value
13:  end for
14:  for Xgb Functions do
15:    t:optimize nrounds,c,eta,lambda,alpha to reduce OOB
16:    Create new model t1 combine the function from Step 5 and
     Step 6
17:  end for
18:  for Function t1 do
19:    Predict new data using majority votes based on final model
     t1
20:    Predict the result using testing data
21:  end for
22:  Print the result
23:  return
24: end procedure

```

3 PRELIMINARY RESULTS

From Table 2 it shows that the result of accuracy is consistent in the range of 0.91% to 0.98%. From the result it can be observed that the percentage of accuracy of RF+Xgb improve compare to only the prediction with RF and Xgb separately. In this research also, it is noticed that when doing the hybrid the range of accuracy for all of the dimension is in a constant range. This breaks the gap from previous research done by several researchers in the area of predicting the learning style using an automated approach [3]. Where in the previous research, some researchers having a problem of not manage to get a good accuracy for certain dimension and some research also exclude some dimension as it is not compatible with their

Table 1: Attributes match to Dimension of FLSM

No	Attribute Name	Description of Attribute	Learning Style	Dimension
1	Forum Post	Post more often in discussion forum	Active	PROCESSING
2	Forum View	Reading post but rarely posting by themselves	Reflective	
3	Self assessment	Perform more self-assessment tests	Active	
4	Text Materials	Prefers learning material in textual form	Reflective	
5	Concrete Materials	Prefers concrete learning materials (facts, data) 7	Sensing	PERCEPTION
6	Abstract Materials	Prefer abstract learning material (definition, theories, syntax, flowcharts)	Intuitive	
7	Examples	Prefer examples	Sensing	
8	Exercise rev	Prefers to review answers in graded exercise tests	Intuitive	
9	Visual Materials	Prefers learning materials supplemented with pictures, diagrams, graphs	Visual	INPUT
10	Video Materials	Prefers learning material presented in text or audio	Visual	
11	Text Materials	Prefers learning material in text or audio	Verbal	
12	Forum Post	Post more often in discussion forum	Verbal	
13	Course overview	Prefers overviews, outlines	Global	UNDERSTANDING
14	Nav euclidean distance	Prefers to go through the course step by step (linear)	Sequential	
15	Nav euclidean distance	Prefers to skipping the material (non-linear way)	Global	

model. But, from the result shown it can be observed that the gap can be overcome by having the best model, where in this research it is the combination of RF+Xgb that manage to fulfill the gap by producing a better percentage of accuracy.

Table 2: Comparison of Percentage of Accuracy for Tree-based Algorithm with RF+Xgb

Dimension	RF	Xgb	RF + Xgb
Input	0.94	0.91	0.97
Perception	0.95	0.83	0.97
Processing	0.95	0.92	0.98
Understanding	0.86	0.79	0.91

The value of accuracy for each of the dimension is calculated and compared with literature. From Table 3, the percentage of accuracy when doing a hybrid shows a consistent improvement. The comparison of the classification accuracy is tabulated in Table 3. The result is compared with previous work from literature which use the same learning theory FLSM, but without any hybrid of algorithm.

Table 3: Comparison of Average accuracy results with literature

Method	Average Accuracy
RF+Xgb	0.96 (1)
LSID-ANN[6]	0.81 (3)
J48 [5]	0.89 (2)
DeLeS [7]	0.79 (4)

The increase of accuracy of the current hybrid method of RF+xgb is higher compared to previous literature. It increase by 0.07 when compared with research done by Renato [5]. This improvement in the accuracy of learning style identification can make a significant difference for students. It means a more accurate identification of a students learning style and thus, more accurate information, interventions and advice for students [6]. This will also lead to a better adaptivity of the learning systems. In future, this research will evaluate further the performance of the model by using different evaluation measure that can proved the particular model is the best model.

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